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CLOSING THE GAP BETWEEN FORK AND FARM FOR
CIRCULAR NUTRIENT FLOWS

BUILDING THE GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

Funded by
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

P2GreeN, a Horizon Europe Innovation Action, aims to transform the linear resource and nutrient flows within the agri-food supply chain into a circular system connecting urban and rural areas. By following the 3R principle - Reduce, Reuse, Recover - P2GreeN focuses on restoring the water-agri-food system and promoting sustainable food practices. The project provides innovative alternatives to reduce dependency on mineral fertilizers, offering green bio-based fertilizers to alleviate pressure on natural resources, particularly water and soil. To achieve these goals, P2GreeN will develop blueprints and governance solutions for the transition from "fork to farm," eliminating nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) by establishing circular nutrient flows between urban and rural infrastructures.

Central to the project is to ensure, that diverse perspectives, needs, and expertise of key players across the urban-rural spectrum are integrated into the process of P2GreeN's pilot regions, in Gotland in Sweden, the metropolitan area of North German Plain, and the La Axarquía region in Spain. In these regions, P2GreeN is implementing and testing circular value chains that recover N and P from human excreta to produce safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture use. The insights and experiences gained will be used to replicate and expand these circular solutions in four follower regions - Hungary, Italy, France, and Greece. The implementations in P2GreeN's pilot and follower regions requires active collaboration between policymakers, farmers, urban planners, businesses, and local communities.

By involving stakeholders from the beginning, the project addresses socio-economic and cultural barriers, aligns solutions with local needs, and fosters ownership and commitment to the project's objectives. Furthermore, stakeholder input is vital for creating effective governance frameworks and business models that are feasible and scalable across different regions. Engaging stakeholders also supports the replication of P2Green's circular economy models in varied contexts, helping to ensure that the project's innovative solutions are adopted and sustained long-term across Europe. All insights in this booklet derive from several stakeholder co-creation workshops in the pilot regions. All documentation and methodology can be found in P2Green's deliverable 4.3.

Deliverables

CONTENT

Executive Summary	1
The Spanish pilot region	4
Overview: Water scarcity and agricultural challenges in La Axarquía Region in Malaga	4
Challenges, needs, and benefits of local stakeholders in Spain	9
Strategies to address the challenges and needs of local stakeholders in Spain	11
The German pilot region	13
Overview: Nutrient recycling and sanitation innovations in the North German Plain	13
Identified challenges, needs, and benefits of local stakeholders in Germany	18
Strategies to address the challenges and needs of local stakeholders in Germany	20
The Swedish pilot region	23
Overview: Nutrient recycling challenges in Gotland	23
Challenges, needs, and benefits of local stakeholders in Sweden	28
Strategies to address the challenges and needs of local stakeholders in Sweden	30
Summary for all three pilot regions: stakeholder engagement strategies across	32
References	35

THE SPANISH PILOT REGION

OVERVIEW: WATER SCARCITY AND AGRICULTURAL CHALLENGES IN LA AXARQUÍA REGION IN MALAGA

La Axarquía, a key sub-tropical agricultural region in southern Spain (Andalusia), faces severe water scarcity, groundwater overuse, and desertification risks. Freshwater resources are increasingly strained due to a growing population, tourism and high agricultural water demands. Within Spain, around 30% of irrigated land is located in Andalusia, which is also one of the driest regions of the country. Further, the high production level led to one of the highest greenhouse concentrations worldwide and overexploitation of groundwater (Gallego-Valero et al., 2019; López-Serrano et al., 2021). For example, avocado and mango crops, prevalent in the region of La Axarquía, require constant irrigation throughout the entire season, making reclaimed water an invaluable resource to supplement decreasing freshwater sources during dry spells. This approach could not only safeguard the environment but also support economic resilience by ensuring a consistent water supply for agricultural production, even during droughts.

At the P2Green test site, technology provider Bioazul is employing a Water Reclamation Plant to produce reclaimed water using treated wastewater, after secondary treatment, from the municipal wastewater treatment plant in Algarrobo. The advanced tertiary treatment ensures the removal of pathogens, suspended solids, and other contaminants, transforming the treated wastewater into nutrient-rich effluent. This process can produce 3650 m³ of reclaimed water per year. Reclaimed water is then used to fertigate avocado and mango crops and, if needed, it is supplemented by mineral fertilizers or diluted with local water, under the control of an innovative smart fertigation tool (SFT). The SFT provides information on nutrient levels, and elements in the soil affecting the development of crops. The Spanish test site is fostering a sustainable and circular approach to nutrient and water resource utilization in the region. The field trials and governance development with local authorities, aim to counteract drought risks, avoid soil pollution, and raise awareness among farmers and other relevant stakeholders.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS

Forefront of Europe: The EU reuses about 2.4% of treated wastewater (~1,000 Hm³/year), with Spain leading at nearly 50% of the total volume and ranking fifth globally. Around 27% of Spain's 2,000 wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) use advanced tertiary treatments, though reuse is concentrated in water-scarce regions like Murcia, where 90% of wastewater is reclaimed, primarily for agriculture (IDRA, 2021).

Water scarcity: Increasing droughts, high desalination costs, and rising water demands for agriculture and green spaces are intensifying wastewater reuse. Scholars suggest transforming treatment plants into biofactories to enhance resource recovery. Reclaimed water holds promise as a valuable contributor to urban water supplies through direct use or indirect support of the conventional wastewater systems. However, the increasing presence of new pollutants and the flows of increased stormwaters, due to climate changes, are present challenges that wastewater treatment plants need to address (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021). Increasing wastewater scarcity could lead to conflicts among farmers, businesses, and policymakers (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021).

Sustainable agriculture & policy: Reclaimed water supports sustainable farming, with over 40% of Spain's reused wastewater going to irrigation, while industrial use accounts for just 10%. The Royal Decree 1620/2007 established legal frameworks, but scholars call for mechanisms to enhance reuse quality and promote regenerative agriculture (Jodar-Abellan, López-Ortiz & Melgarejo-Moreno, 2019).

Technological advances & challenges: Improved wastewater treatment can cut costs and reduce fertilizer use by up to 66% (López-Serrano et al., 2021), benefiting soil fertility and crop quality. However, reclaimed water remains costly compared to natural sources, and infrastructure challenges hinder widespread adoption. Expanding treatment and distribution systems is crucial for making reclaimed water a sustainable, cost-effective resource.

Acceptance of reclaimed water: Especially, the public concern over pollution and pathogens is highlighted. Concerns about reclaimed water can be divided into:

- **Consumer-level concerns** about the sanitary safety of reclaimed water and whether it is safe to consume food irrigated with reclaimed water are major concerns. The acceptance of reclaimed water usage for irrigation is connected to cultural norms. Especially, concerns about sanitary risks enforce the stigma associated with using treated wastewater for agriculture. Additionally, Ballesteros-Olza et al. (2022) describe a 'yuck factor' they recognized at a test site in the greater Madrid area. They observed disgusted reactions of stakeholders at the idea of using reclaimed water on fruit crops. Additionally, the perception of sanitary risks by consumers is described as a critical factor in advancing the use of reclaimed water for irrigation.
- **Farmer-level concerns** about the water quality (salt content, electrical conductivity) and the potential negative impact on crops are additional concerns. However, farmers seem to be aware of the potential of reclaimed water to secure water supply, fertilize, provide nutrients, as well as being a cost-saving alternative to fresh water (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). Mesa-Pérez and Berbel (2020) highlight that the perception of key stakeholders differs depending on the level of water scarcity and the significance of irrigated agriculture in their immediate context.

Public awareness & education: Spain emphasizes governance and market strategies to boost societal acceptance of reclaimed water. Regulation EU-2020/741[3] sets minimum water reuse standards, but also highlights long-term public education. Despite many positive aspects derived from the use of treated wastewater to irrigate crops, its low implementation rate seems to be connected to farmers' perceptions due to the persistent inability to receive the economic, social, and environmental benefits derived from its use. Literature highlights the need to illustrate the economic benefits to farmers to enhance long-term sustainability in the agricultural sector (López-Serrano, et al., 2021). Examples from regions like Murcia (IDRA, 2021), with a high percentage of wastewater reuse could support social acceptance and function as upscaling case scenario.

REGULATORY LANDSCAPE & INSTITUTIONAL BARRIERS

EU regulations and Spain's legal framework promote wastewater reuse, but lack of institutional coordination, complex regulations, and administrative delays impede progress. Further political support and streamlined policies are needed to facilitate implementation and encourage farmer adoption.

EU directives and regulations: EU directives and regulations, including Directive 91/271/EEC [4] and the Water Framework Directive (WFD) [5], advocate for the cost-recovery principle in water-related services. In 2018, the EU proposed regulations to encourage water reuse for agricultural irrigation and environmental purposes and this legislation enabled wastewater reclamation and reuse in Spain. Consequently, taxes in Spain have been adjusted to fund wastewater treatment services and improve water quality (Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020). Especially, agricultural water abstraction mechanisms were implemented. These systems aim to recuperate the expenses associated with regulation, storage, and management of basin-level water services. They align with the requirements outlined in the WFD, with different levels of cost recovery being observed (Berbel et al., 2019). Since 2020, reclaimed water is also part of the EU's circular economy actions, with regulation 2020/741 [3] aiming to standardize reclaimed water quality and risk management systems across member states. This, along with global initiatives like the UN 2030 Agenda, the Sustainable Development Goals, and the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, promotes wider adoption of reclaimed water usage for irrigation, offering a promising solution amid water resource pressures (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022; Mesa-Pérez & Berbel, 2020).

Safety standards on national level: The EU Water Reuse Regulation [6] is anticipated to promote reclaimed water use in agriculture. This regulation is expected to address trade barriers for agricultural products, establish standardized water quality requirements, and enhance social acceptance through improved risk management processes (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). Agricultural extensification and public awareness campaigns both led to positive outcomes as stressed by Ballesteros-Olza et al. (2022).

However, only public awareness initiatives increased water reuse, while agricultural extensification primarily reduced water abstractions and pollution. In Spain, wastewater treatment and reuse are regulated by the EU Directive of 1991 on Urban Wastewater Treatment, which aims to protect the environment from the adverse effects of urban wastewater discharges. The directive is incorporated into Spanish law 11/95 and by the Spanish Royal Decree 1620/2007 on reuse of treated wastewater [2]. Besides the fact that Spain was fined for not complying with EU standards, the country holds a leading position in Europe regarding water reuse, primarily for agricultural irrigation (Rodríguez-Villanueva & Sauri, 2021).

Lack of institutional coordination on a local level: The use of reclaimed water for irrigation is hampered by institutional aspects, public resistance, and high costs (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022). Lack of institutional coordination, complex regulations, and delays imposed by administrative procedures are identified as barriers. Supportive frameworks and clear institutional arrangements are needed to facilitate reclaimed water reuse projects. Political support could facilitate the bureaucratic process and foster reclaimed water use (Ballesteros-Olza et al., 2022).

FUTURE CHALLENGES & OPPORTUNITIES

Overall, reclaimed water presents a sustainable solution for La Axarquía's water crisis, but overcoming social, economic, and regulatory barriers is crucial for its success. Spain must address emerging pollutants such as pharmaceutical residues and microplastics in wastewater. The EU Green Deal and Spain's National Water Plan push for increased water reuse and circular economy models, opening doors for sustainable sanitation innovations. Advancements in phosphorus recovery, decentralized wastewater treatment, and nutrient recycling could drive Spain's transition towards a more sustainable water and agricultural system.

CHALLENGES, NEEDS, AND BENEFITS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN SPAIN

The **challenges** identified focus on governance, building effective networks, and mediating with administrative bodies. Efficient management of reclaimed water is crucial, along with reducing associated costs and overcoming societal resistance to its use. Raising awareness and promoting best practices are necessary, to increase access to digital tools and systems for both farmers and administrators. Key technical challenges include calculating precise irrigation and nutrient doses, implementing "water on demand" strategies, and utilizing real-time data processing with sensors. Scaling up treatment technologies and adapting infrastructures to make reclaimed water more accessible, while ensuring its quality, are also critical. Additionally, there is a need to study the nutrient content of reclaimed water, reduce its potential impact on soil, and estimate crop water requirements when using reclaimed water (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Overview of identified challenges and needs in the Spanish pilot region. Summary of co-creation workshop in 2022.

To address these challenges, the identified **needs** include encouraging the use of various water sources and addressing the current lack of training. Raising public awareness and promoting best practices are essential to the process, along with increasing knowledge and training around digital tools for the general public. Adaptation of European regulations and clear guidelines are necessary, as well as implementing a more sustainable agri-food system.

The **benefits** of addressing these needs include economic and energy savings and reduced water and fertilizer consumption. Digitization can enable precise nutrient and irrigation dosing based on crop needs, contributing to sustainable agriculture and the promotion of a circular economy (CE). These changes would promote a reduction in water and carbon footprints, less waste, and increased water availability.

Stakeholders can **contribute** to governance and infrastructure by lobbying relevant administrations, developing recommendations, and creating synergies through projects. They can propose and develop new projects, secure funding, and operational plans. In education, stakeholders can share success stories, promote P2Green results, and raise public awareness through campaigns, workshops, and conferences. They can also offer training on reclaimed water use, legislation, and risk management, and promote CE partnerships. Economically, stakeholders can help develop technology for reclaimed water, share data, and work on R&D projects to break the status quo. They can develop platforms and tools for better data utilization, provide expert consulting, and integrate Internet of Things (IoT) sensors and other digital tools into agriculture and industry.

STRATEGIES TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES AND NEEDS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN SPAIN

Step 3 Strategy development

Your pilot - Potential solutions to overcome challenges faced in the stakeholder engagement process

Figure 2: Strategies to address the challenges and needs of local stakeholders in Spain. Outcomes from projects co-creation workshop 2023.

Based on co-creation workshops carried out with the pilot partners, stakeholder engagement strategies for local actors were developed.

- **Low effort/low impact:** Increasing dissemination and communication activities at the pilot partner level, such as improving visibility on the websites of partners or disseminating targeted communication material, is a simple but limited strategy.
- **Medium effort/medium impact:** Exploring new sectors for the application of P2Green's solutions, such as gardening and landscaping, offers moderate effort with potential to broaden engagement and create new synergies. Improving and adapting the message to fit different audiences is another valuable approach that requires thoughtful consideration but can yield significant results.

- **Low effort/high impact:** Leveraging existing synergies with the project's network and related initiatives can enhance visibility and stakeholder interest with relatively low effort. Translating P2GreenN's social media presence into Spanish can also expand its reach to a broader audience in a straightforward and impactful manner.
- **High effort/medium impact:** Directly reaching out to farmers by attending their meetings and briefly engaging with them could also prove highly effective, though it demands significant time and effort. Similarly, acknowledging stakeholder participation through incentives or small tokens of appreciation can enhance relationships and build long-term trust.
- **High effort/high impact:** The most impactful action involves reaching the right authorities, farmers, and stakeholders through targeted communication strategies. This requires a considerable investment of resources, but it can lead to deep, meaningful engagement with key players.

THE GERMAN PILOT REGION

OVERVIEW: NUTRIENT RECYCLING AND SANITATION INNOVATIONS IN THE NORTH GERMAN PLAIN

Germany faces growing water and soil pollution due to industrial activity, intensive farming, and climate change. Agricultural runoff and wastewater discharges contribute to high nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution, affecting 65% of rivers and 41% of groundwater (Gruère, Shigemitsu & Crawford, 2020). Climate change exacerbates these issues, increasing extreme weather events that challenge sewage systems. Germany has a well-established wastewater system, with 96% of households connected to centralized treatment plants. However, this infrastructure limits innovation in sanitation and nutrient recovery (DWA, 2010).

The German pilot region, located in the North German plain, tests two distinct pathways of fertilizer production. Through a urine treatment system, with a treatment capacity for approximately 100 m³/yr urine, provided by VunaNexus, a safe fertilizer Aurin®, is produced and will be marketed. The biological treatment involves urine nitrification, which transforms 50% of ammonia into nitrate while simultaneously eliminating micropollutants and pathogens. On an additional test site, a thermophilic container-based composting system for feces is set up and operated. The human feces stem from dry toilets collected by Goldeimer. The process involves the decomposition and recomposition of solid matter mixed with additional bulk material using an automated auger system, resulting in the production of a recycling fertilizer. The Vagtshoff farmers provide industrial waste heat and biochar for the composting facility, as well as the agricultural area (10 ha) for fertiliser application. Both, faecal compost (~40 t[dm]/yr) and Aurin® fertilisers will be used to grow agricultural crops. During the project period, changes regarding pilot partners in the German pilot took place (2nd Amendment).

SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS

Need for circular solutions: Climate change impacts drive demand for closed-loop systems to recover nutrients and reduce waste. Circular production models, like City Regional Food Systems (CRFS), interconnect urban and agricultural sectors to enhance sustainability (Keuter et al., 2021; Nelles, Grünes & Morscheck, 2016). The German association of water management (DWA) describes novel sanitary systems (NASS) as an alternative, promising higher flexibility in adapting to changing environmental conditions. Neligan (2018) further highlights the need to increase the digitalisation of such processes, to ensure an efficient resource recovery from human excreta.

Market growth & demand: Rising scarcity of phosphorus and nitrogen, coupled with freshwater shortages, increases the market potential for nutrient recovery technologies. Mobile dry toilets and alternative fertilizers are gaining traction. Additionally, the demand for alternative fertilizers is on the rise as a substitute for chemical fertilizers (Dadrasina et al., 2021). Neligan (2018) highlights that the private sector plays a key role in shifting towards a more circular approach and resource recovery. The scholar argues that resource scarcity is pressuring the German economy towards resource efficiency, fostering both economic and environmental self-interest in the efficient use of materials. Horbach and Rammer (2020) argue that, despite initial implementation costs, circular innovations in waste recycling eventually lead to cost efficiency.

Success stories & public perception: Case studies, such as projects in Hamburg and Eschborn (Skambraks et al., 2016), demonstrate the feasibility of recycled fertilizers and help increase social acceptance. However, broad adoption requires regulatory support and education. Committed stakeholders as well as strong sustainable project drivers are also defined as enablers of a successful implementation.

Furthermore, a long-term engagement strategy aiming for broad acceptance is argued to be important for successful implementation and usage (Arnold & Schmidt, 2012). Skambraks et al. (2016) argue that early-stage pilot sites are driven by university and academic collaborations, while test sites in later stages are supported by governmental collaborations and initiatives. Successful projects and pilot test sites are defined as essential prerequisites for long-term implementation and upscaling (Skambraks et al., 2016).

Regulatory & economic barriers: While pilot projects show upscale potential, legal restrictions on recycled fertilizers and bureaucratic hurdles slow adoption. Initial high costs also deter investment, despite long-term economic benefits. Skambraks et al. (2016) underscore the challenges associated with implementing new and innovative infrastructure systems. For instance, uncertainties in assigning stakeholder responsibilities, rigid organizational structures, financial concerns, and unclear legal regulations can impede growth for companies in the sector.

Knowledge acquisition: When implementing source separation technologies, it is considered essential to gather information on user acceptance, regulatory requirements and cross-sectorial stakeholder networks. For this, designated pilot areas can serve as means to gain insights into the overall environmental impacts and societal performance during their operational phases (Skambraks, 2016). Further, Keuter et al. (2021) argue that innovative processes such as bio-based fertilizer production need to be integrated into long-term social transformation processes to enhance the acceptance of food derived from recycled materials. Moreover, there is a desire for cross-sectorial collaboration among stakeholders and experts. A notable internal motivation, as highlighted by actors involved in current and forthcoming pilot projects, is the pursuit of knowledge to effectively tackle potential future challenges in wastewater treatment (Skambraks, 2016).

Education and social acceptance: Krause et al. (2021) highlight the importance of educating stakeholders and the general public on the correct usage of new innovations. For example, easily accessible information and clear guidelines can support social acceptance. Additionally, conducting tests for harmful substances in accordance with local laws and regulations and guaranteeing the production of safe and high-quality fertilizers, can increase social acceptance. Education also needs to be implemented in the overall process to improve the reception of food grown with bio-based fertilizer (Keuter et al., 2021).

REGULATORY LANDSCAPE & CHALLENGES

Germany's legal framework, shaped by EU policies like the Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan, promotes sustainability but also imposes strict regulations that hinder the reuse of human waste as fertilizer. Key barriers include:

The German Circular Economy Act (Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz KrWG) [7]: Formulation of a waste prevention program (first introduced in 2012) to promote circular economy and preserve natural resources and ensure the protection of people and the environment with focus on production and management of waste. To improve the recycling of waste, the obligation to collect waste separately should be strengthened.

Resource Efficiency Program III (2020-2023) [8]: Developing and implementing concepts and procedures to recover phosphorus and other valuable materials from municipal wastewater. The goal is to further develop wastewater and waste treatment from a previously hygiene-focused system to a resource-oriented one.

DIN-SPEC-91421: is a quality standardization approach of bio-fertilizers derived from human waste. The product specifications (DIN, 2020) aim to enhance the marketability of recycling products in both the German and European markets, thereby facilitating industry development. This effort also seeks to make a sustainability contribution by promoting the establishment of integrated circular economies, achieved through nutrient recycling, and connecting sanitation and food production.

German bio-waste regulation (BioAbfV) [10]: This amendment includes the list of bio-waste types and other materials suitable for the utilisation on agricultural land. Human excreta or sewage sludge are not defined as waste and therefore not approved for re-use.

German wastewater ordinance (AbfKlärV) [11]: The regulation defines conditions under which soil-related utilisation of sewage sludge (for fertilisation purposes or for agricultural backfilling) is permissible. It stipulates that all treatment plants must determine the phosphorus content of their sewage sludge and outline how phosphorus recovery is to be implemented by 2032. Due to high contamination of sewage sludge, recycling to soils has been halted. Regulations such as the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) further reduce the effluent concentration of phosphorous in Germany.

Fertilizer ordinance (Düngemittelverordnung DüMV) [9]: The DüMV defines that only raw materials listed as permissible in Annex 2 Table 7 of this ordinance may be used for fertilizer production. There is a prohibition on the use of unlisted substances. This includes human feces and urine as raw materials, and consequently, the resulting recycled fertilizer (see § 3(1) of the Fertilizer ordinance) (ZirkulierBAR, 2022). In particular, the inapplicability of the BioAbfV (Biowaste Ordinance) [10] and the DüMV (Fertilizer Ordinance) [9] prevents the production and promotion of recycling fertilizers. This constitutes a significant obstacle to the advancement of recycling fertilizers in Germany. Under the classification of human waste as wastewater, is a very limited utilization pathway through the AbfKlärV (Wastewater Treatment Ordinance) [11]. However, the subsequent use of the fertilizer is limited, excluding economic market opportunities.

FUTURE CHALLENGES & OPPORTUNITIES

A significant future challenge for humans and farming lies in eliminating unaccounted pollutants in wastewater, such as pharmaceutical residues, hormone-like chemicals, microplastics and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). German regulations assume that the current wastewater treatment methods cannot address these trace substances. Emerging technologies like special membranes for nutrient recovery seem promising for circular nutrient recovery from human waste.

However, there are no established legal standards to guide sewage plant operators in their transition to more resource-oriented sewage methods. Additionally, the fertilisation with recycling fertilizers is currently forbidden in the German market. The ministry of environment is currently developing a "trace substance strategy" that could pave the path for water reuse.

IDENTIFIED CHALLENGES, NEEDS, AND BENEFITS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN GERMANY

The identified **challenges** in the German pilot region include a lack of clarity and safety in the envisioned outcomes of the transformation, as well as difficulties with the certification of fertilizers and the guarantees offered to product standards. There is a need to ensure acceptance of recycling fertilizers by farmers, but legal and governance barriers, particularly for decentralized sanitation approaches, pose significant obstacles. Additionally, there is a shortage of real-life demonstrations and effective communication of scientific results to the broader society. The public "yuk" factor, alongside fear and doubt surrounding new approaches, further hinders the extension of nutrient recovery from human waste. These challenges are exacerbated by the urgency of transformation processes, which are complex and time-consuming, and an economic system that currently favours non-circular and fossil-based systems. There is also a general misconception that ecological options are less economically viable, making it harder to engage companies in the circular economy. Moreover, without legislative changes, the collection and exploitation of feces remains impractical. Achieving investors and decision-makers support, ensuring the safety of fertilizers, and making circular economy models more practical are critical issues, especially when dealing with cross-sectoral topics that intersect various legal frameworks (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Overview of identified challenges and needs in the German pilot region. Summary of co-creation workshop in 2022.

Addressing these challenges requires several key **needs** to be met. First, there must be clarification of legislative processes to replicate P2Green value chains effectively. There is also a need to apply recommendations for agri-business operators, along with the identification of decision-makers and influencers who can support these initiatives. Investment and financing options are necessary, as is the identification of companies capable of transformative operations. Ecological considerations, such as the need for more information on current sanitation challenges and strategies to save and reuse water, are essential. Additionally, clear documentation of results is needed for effective dissemination. Particularly, in terms of what is demanded from local stakeholders regarding risks associated with using fertilisers derived from human excreta. Collaboration between scientific communities and other societal forces is also crucial, and identifying local knowledge carriers is important for the creation of a knowledge repository. Finally, generating a positive public narrative around these topics will aid in overcoming resistance.

The identified **benefits** of addressing these challenges include the creation of supportive networks, facilitating the exchange of experiences related to barriers and enablers, and the establishment of quality standards for nutrient recycling and bio-based fertilizers. There is also potential for job-creation in rural areas and the growing demand for organic fertilizers in regenerative agriculture.

Stakeholders can **contribute** to various aspects of governance and infrastructure by helping establish fertilizer quality standards, securing local funding, lobbying for legislative amendments, and communicating with investors about the reliability of investments. They can also contribute to education by organizing local events, forming networks for experience exchange, and developing replicable blueprints for fertilizer application. In the economic sphere, stakeholders can assist in capacity building, job creation, and the development of value chains and business cases. However, certain areas, such as fertilizer certification, quality assurance, and cost calculation for different target groups, remain outside the scope of what stakeholders can contribute.

STRATEGIES TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES AND NEEDS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN GERMANY

Step 3 Strategy development

Your pilot - Potential solutions to overcome challenges faced in the stakeholder engagement process

Can be done immediately

Figure 4: Strategies to address the challenges and needs of local stakeholders in Germany. Outcomes from projects co-creation workshop 2023.

Based on co-creation workshops carried out with the pilot partners stakeholder engagement strategies for local actors were developed.

- **Low effort/low impact:** Solutions like utilizing ChatGPT for automation or emphasizing resilience in messaging require minimal effort but will likely have limited effects.
- **Low effort/medium impact:** Sending and showcasing products to stakeholders could have some moderate impact. Additionally, connecting messages to binding political agendas can help build stakeholder relevance.
- **Low effort/high impact:** Shifting away from a "hippie, poopie" image, talking about tangible benefits such as money, jobs, and markets, and presenting the project as reversible can yield significant benefits without a large investment of resources. Inviting stakeholders to visit pilot sites or living labs, establishing a key reference project, and creating an internal ambassador for local authorities are also actions that require rather low effort but promise high returns.
- **Medium effort/low impact:** Learning from other sectors such as the climate debate and understanding the most effective measures versus ineffective approaches can enhance engagement with a reasonable amount of effort but might have limited immediate impact.
- **Medium effort/medium impact:** Attracting stakeholders through entertainment (e.g. keynote speakers), adapting project approaches to the specific needs of different territories, and focusing on farmer cooperatives using a bottom-up approach offer moderate impact for the effort invested. Engaging powerful NGOs to support the project can also foster stronger alliances.
- **Medium effort/high impact:** Engaging in discussions that create emotions (such as through art) and getting out of a purely normative approach could have a significant influence on stakeholder relationships and project visibility.

- **High effort/medium impact:** Listening to the voices of farmers and convincing influential figures can help bring the project into broader public awareness, though this will require significant time and resources. Similarly, identifying the right contact person and exerting pressure on ministries are high-effort strategies that could yield solid results.
- **High effort/high impact:** The most effective but resource-intensive actions include lobbying for policy changes, building bridges of trust with stakeholders, changing administrative mechanisms, and increasing the lobbying budget. Establishing KPIs with authorities (e.g. expanding the number of living labs), defining specific tasks for stakeholders, and creating meaningful connections by avoiding marginal contacts are high-effort strategies with the potential for substantial impact.

THE SWEDISH PILOT REGION

OVERVIEW: NUTRIENT RECYCLING CHALLENGES IN GOTLAND

Sweden, particularly Gotland, faces severe eutrophication and hypoxia due to high nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) levels in wastewater. While 90% of Swedish households are connected to advanced wastewater treatment plants, traditional systems still release 38% of nitrogen and 29% of phosphorus from human waste into surface waters. About 25% of sludge is reused in agriculture, but concerns over heavy metals and micropollutants limit further nutrient recycling. Sweden's infrastructural lock-in also hampers large-scale implementation of source separation technologies. Sweden has been a pioneer in urine diversion since the 1990s, but early initiatives failed due to technological inefficiencies and poor integration with existing wastewater infrastructure. Recently, with EU policies like the Green Deal and Horizon 2020, source separation is regaining interest. Several Swedish municipalities are now testing urine-diversion toilets (~135,000 urine-diversion toilets installed, mostly in summer houses and allotments) (McConville et al., 2017a).

Within P2GeeN, the Swedish pilot site aims to transform human urine into dry fertilizer for barley cultivation. The Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU) and Sanitation360, demonstrate nutrient recycling from human urine. In the urban area of Visby, processes for urine collection, stabilisation for nutrient retention and solid fertilizer production will be expanded. The resulting fertilizer is utilized in agriculture for barley cultivation, ultimately contributing to local beer production at Gotland's Bryggeri. This initiative creates a new value chain, reducing nutrient loads in wastewater, enhancing local agriculture and food production. The reclamation potential of this process for collection at public toilets and urinals is estimated at 900 kg of nitrogen and 90 kg of phosphorous per year. Furthermore, the pilot aims to obtain 150 m³ of urine by the end of 2026. The test site especially aims to demonstrate a full-service chain of nutrient recovery focusing on awareness raising, and capacity building with municipalities, farmers, and other relevant stakeholders in Sweden.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS

Phosphorus & resource limitations: While phosphorus supply concerns have eased, recycling remains crucial to prevent future scarcity ("Phosphogeddon"). Highlighting the limited availability of resources can encourage the exploration of alternative fertilizers, such as those derived from human sanitary waste. The discussions in Sweden have moved over from only focusing on the re-circulation of phosphorus into also including the recycling of nitrogen. The growing interest in urine source separation, particularly in Europe, is environmentally advantageous and relies on the ability to replace synthetic fertilizers with a product that has low nitrogen emissions (Shirai, Leisz & Kyuma, 2023).

Climate change & Circular Economy: Increased environmental degradation and water scarcity drive interest in urine-derived fertilizers, reducing reliance on synthetic fertilizers. There is a shift towards recognizing urine as a valuable resource, rich in nutrients, which can be used for fertilizing crops or integrated into industrial processes (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021). Scholars argue that about 5% of P and 30% N are emitted with the outgoing wastewater from treatment plants when they reach their treatment requirements. The trend towards sustainable resource usage can empower businesses that offer eco-friendly solutions, such as converting human waste to fertilizers (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021).

Infrastructure lock-in: Sweden's centralized wastewater system makes it difficult to integrate new recovery technologies, slowing adoption. This trend highlights the challenges faced by businesses trying to introduce innovative waste-to-fertilizer solutions in regions with established infrastructure (McConville, et al., 2017a; McConville et al, 2017b).

Emerging test sites: The P2Green test site in Gotland is part of a global trend wherein efforts are made to separate urine from sewage and recycle it into products such as fertilizer (McConville et al., 2017a). This approach, known as urine diversion, is not only being explored in Gotland but also countries such as the United States, Australia, Switzerland, Ethiopia, and South Africa.

Cultural taboos: There are broader questions of social change and acceptance related to varying levels of cultural taboos around human waste and deeply entrenched conventions about industrial sewage and food systems. This suggests that cultural norms and societal conventions can act as barriers to the acceptance of using human waste as fertilizer (Wald, 2022). In line with this argument, McConville et al. (2017a) highlight the importance of social acceptance as a prerequisite for a long-term implementation of source separation and nutrient recycling technologies.

Farmer preferences: Parfitt (2023) indicates that the physical form and usability of bio-fertilizers can influence its acceptance and usage degree. For example, most farmers in Gotland viewed Sanitation360's dry and pelletized fertilizer favourably. With their experience in spreading this type of fertilizer, farmers can also utilize existing machinery and spreading methods that are compatible with it.

Conflict of values: In Sweden, there are strong values regarding the public and economic good, which can conflict with environmental priorities and hinder sustainable developments. Conflicting values are also observed in the expansion of the predominant centralized wastewater system or in supporting the establishment of a decentralized approach. Further, values which may drive transition towards nutrient recycling are economic efficiency, risk reduction and the maintenance of existing sewage and wastewater treatment systems (McConville et al., 2017a).

Knowledge and awareness: Many farmers have not been informed about the regulations and possibilities surrounding the use of human urine in agriculture due to such information being presented in jargon-filled legal documents and publications. This lack of awareness can act as a barrier to adopting new farming techniques or adjusting existing technologies and infrastructure (Parfitt, 2023).

Consumer acceptance: There is a divide among experts about consumer acceptance of food fertilized with recycling fertilizer. While some believe consumers do not consider the type of fertilizer used, others think consumers might find it repellent or unsafe. This indicates that consumer perception can be a significant factor in the adoption of such fertilizers, additionally source separated urine often falls under same rules as sewage sludge and is looked upon as sludge, leading to a challenging situation to reuse it as a clean fertiliser. One further challenge is the food industry not wanting to take risk, thereby not accepting circular fertilisers with the motive that the consumers may not accept it. Additionally, prejudices about the safety of recycling fertilizer need to be overcome across Sweden. The current sanitation system and decades long negative media coverage of the use of sewage sludge in agriculture in Sweden, has likely sensitized the public's view towards the potential use of urine in agriculture as well (Parfitt, 2023).

REGULATORY LANDSCAPE & CHALLENGES

Sweden has several regulations supporting sustainable sanitation and nutrient recycling, but gaps in standardization hinder large-scale adoption:

National Strategy for Sustainable Development: In December 2020, the Swedish parliament approved a government bill with an overarching objective for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda. Sweden will implement the 2030 Agenda to achieve economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable development through a coherent policy nationally and internationally. Implementation will be guided by the agenda's 'leave no one behind' principle. This strategy can act as a guiding framework for businesses aiming to adopt sustainable practices, including human waste-to-fertilizer conversion (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021).

Circular Economy Delegation: In 2016, the Swedish government appointed a special investigator for Circular Economy (CE) who analysed instruments for promoting product utilization and reducing waste generation. This led to the establishment of a Circular Economy Delegation in 2018, aiming to facilitate a transition to a circular, resource-efficient, and bio-based economy at national and regional levels. Such initiatives can empower businesses in the waste-to-fertilizer domain (Heshmati & Rashidghalam, 2021).

Swedish Environmental Code: Since 2006, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency's Environmental Code for on-site sanitation has shifted from prescribing specific technologies to setting functional requirements. However, these functional requirements do not apply to actions on a household level. This regulatory shift can both enable and restrict businesses depending on their technological solutions (McConville et al., 2017a).

Challenges with source separation on a local level: While municipalities like Helsingborg are exploring source separation within existing wastewater jurisdictions, the practice is still in its development stages. The expansion of wastewater jurisdictions using decentralized technologies and source separation is being explored in other municipalities such as Malmö and Gothenburg. This indicates a trend towards source separation, which can empower businesses (McConville et al., 2017a).

Classification of Waste Fractions: In Sweden, source-separated toilet waste fractions are classified as household waste, making them the responsibility of the municipality and its solid waste service provider. However, the application of the Environmental Code on these fractions is relatively untested, indicating potential regulatory challenges for businesses (McConville et al., 2017a).

Certification of source-separated wastewater fractions (SPCR 178) [15]: Quality assurance for source-separated wastewater fractions under SPCR 178 is a commitment to ensure structured operations and traceability of source-separated wastewater fractions (urine, feces, blackwater, and brown water). The requirements set by the certification system are controlled by RISE, an independent organisation, which contributes to increasing end users' confidence in the product. Within P2Green the pilot aims to meet the certification standards to improve acceptance of their fertilizer.

SNFS 1994:2 [16]: is a Swedish regulation that defines the management and treatment of wastewater. It outlines guidelines and standards for the design, construction, and operation of small-scale wastewater treatment plants and the usage of sewage sludge in agriculture. These regulations aim to ensure that such facilities meet certain quality and environmental standards to protect public health and the environment.

SJVFS 2004:62 [17]: is a law on environmental considerations in agriculture about the application of organic fertilizers. To be classified as bio-fertilizer, human urine-derived fertilizer needs to meet the standards defined by the law.

Lack of streamlined norms: A significant bottleneck for future diffusion is the absence of streamlined norms and standards for urine source-separating technologies. The lack of norms for source-separating toilets can restrict businesses from investing in novel toilet designs (Larsen et al., 2021).

FUTURE CHALLENGES & OPPORTUNITIES

Sweden's strong environmental policies and history of sanitation innovation create a promising market for recycling fertilizers. However, infrastructural challenges, cultural perceptions, and regulatory gaps must be addressed for large-scale adoption. Public education, policy reform, and decentralized wastewater models could drive Sweden's transition toward a circular sanitation economy.

CHALLENGES, NEEDS, AND BENEFITS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN SWEDEN

The identified **challenges** include a lack of incentives and subsidies, as well as vague or absent regulations and policies, which creates uncertainty. There is also an absence of clearly defined stakeholders and responsibilities regarding the collection, treatment, and distribution of resources like urine. Public acceptance and awareness remain low, compounded by a lack of research and development, pilot projects, and essential infrastructure (e.g. third pipes, and skilled plumbers). Furthermore, the high cost of system implementation and components adds to these barriers (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Overview of identified challenges and needs in the Swedish pilot region. Summary of co-creation workshop in 2022.

The identified **needs** include ensuring food and fertilizer security, improving the efficiency of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), and preventing the contamination of water with pharmaceutical and medical residues. These efforts also support climate change mitigation and help prevent eutrophication, consequently reducing excessive algae growth in Swedish water bodies like the Baltic Sea.

The **benefits** of addressing these issues are substantial. They include the production of green-labelled products like fertilizers and beer, circular resource recovery, and the promotion of knowledge sharing on the circular economy (CE). Additionally, reducing greenhouse gas emissions from both fertilizer production and WWTP operations, ensuring compliance with treatment regulations, decreasing dependency on synthetic fertilizers, and enhancing water recovery and recycling are key advantages.

Stakeholders can **contribute** to governance and infrastructure by promoting food and fertilizer security, reducing system costs, and addressing the lack of infrastructure. They can also help improve WWTP efficiency. In the realm of education, stakeholders play a vital role in raising public awareness, transferring knowledge, and fostering research and development. From an ecological perspective, stakeholders can support the prevention of pharmaceutical and medical residue spread, reduce eutrophication, and contribute to climate change mitigation efforts.

STRATEGIES TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES AND NEEDS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN SWEDEN

Step 3 Strategy development

Figure 6: Strategies to address the challenges and needs of local stakeholders in Sweden. Outcomes from projects co-creation workshop 2023.

Based on co-creation workshops carried out with the pilot partners stakeholder engagement strategies for local actors were developed.

- **Low effort/low impact:** Conducting a simple survey to collect feedback on activities of interest from stakeholders and providing short policy briefs on how new directives may affect them are straightforward strategies with limited impact.

- **Low effort/high impact:** Sharing best practices for engaging stakeholders and distributing low-cost promotional materials, like T-shirts and pins, can significantly enhance visibility and encourage participation with minimal effort.
- **Medium effort/medium impact:** Creating infographics and videos in local languages, along with linking the project to broader issues like climate change, requires moderate effort but can increase relevance and understanding across diverse audiences. Regular press releases in local media also boosts visibility.
- **Medium effort/high impact:** Booking stakeholders for events well in advance and following up one-on-one to address specific concerns helps build stronger relationships and ensures participation, though it demands more planning and coordination.
- **High effort/high impact:** Establishing meaningful two-way dialogues with stakeholders and investing in direct communication, like attending stakeholder events and making cold calls, requires substantial resources but leads to deep, lasting engagement.

SUMMARY FOR ALL THREE PILOT REGIONS: STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES ACROSS

The following table provides an overview of challenges, needs and benefits listed by relevant stakeholders in the pilot regions. The challenges and needs identified among stakeholders in the three pilot regions. This overview highlights the importance of a systematic approach that addresses regulatory, societal, technological, and environmental factors

Challenges	Needs	Benefits
<p>Regulatory and Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certification of fertilizers (GER) • Legislative amendments & governance framework (GER) • Lack of incentives and subsidies (SWE) • Lack of regulations & policies (vague and ambiguous) (SWE) • Mediation with administration (SPA) • Efficient management of reclaimed water (SPA) • Cost reduction (SPA) 	<p>Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive voice of the public on the topic (GER) • Awareness raising among citizens, promotion of best practice (SPA) • Increase knowledge and training tools (for the general public) (SPA) 	<p>Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a supportive network on the matter (GER) • Exchange of experiences (on barriers and enablers) (GER)
<p>Society and Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to find or create a broad societal acceptance? (GER) 	<p>Governance and investment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification of legislative processes for the replication of P2Green value chain (GER) • Application recommendations for agri-business operations (GER) • Investment and financing (GER) • Food and fertilizer security (SWE) • Augmenting the efficiency in WWTP (SWE) • Adaptation of European regulations, clear guidelines (SPA) • Investment in infrastructures and sensors (SPA) 	<p>Ecological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular resource recovery (SWE) • Reduced GHG emission from fertilizer production & WWTP (SWE) • Enhancing water recovery and recycling (SWE) • Sustainable agriculture (SPA)

Technology and infrastructure	Ecological	Economic
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making CE more practical (GER) • Investment and planning reliability for investors and decision makers (GER) • Create acceptance of investors and decision-makers (GER) • Knowledge on the potential of fertilization products (GER) • Safety of fertilizers (elimination of pollutants) (GER) • Lack of infrastructure, e.g. third pipe, plumbers (SWE) • Cost of the system (implementation, system components) (SWE) • Calculation of irrigation/nutrient dose (SPA) • Nutrient content of reclaimed water (SPA) • Adapt water quality for its use • Accessibility to digital tools and systems on all levels (farmers/ administrators) (SPA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevention of pharmaceutical, medical residues (SWE) • Climate change mitigation (SWE) • Prevention of eutrophication (excessive growth of algae) (SWE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality standards (GER) • Creation of jobs in rural areas (GER) • Reduce dependency on synthetic fertilizer (SWE) • Economic savings and savings in energy, water, and fertilizer (SPA) • Nutrient/ irrigation dosing adjusted to crop needs through digitization (SPA)

Table 1: Overview of challenges and needs of local stakeholders across all three pilot regions. Summary of co-creation workshop results in 2022.

RECOMMENDED ACTIVITIES TO ENGAGE STAKEHOLDERS ON A REGULAR BASIS

The following table provides an overview of engagement activities across all three pilots. The strategies are targeted to create regional stakeholder networks and collaboration.

Strategy	Output	Target Audience	Frequency	Specific Pilot
Create targeted messages	Targeted, effective messaging. Focus on economic impacts, job creation, market relevance	Farmers, regional authorities, economic actors	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Use effective channels	Utilize online and offline channels, including local platforms			Spain, Sweden
Adjust for local context	Acknowledge diversity within farming communities and territories			Germany, Sweden

Build personal and meaningful relationships	Appoint dedicated communication ambassadors, tangible outcomes	Policymakers, farmers' representatives, NGOs	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Share tangible outcomes	Project progress reports, invitations to test sites			Spain, Sweden
Create synergies	Collaborate with similar projects, co-create events			Germany, Sweden
Be proactive	Research and participate in stakeholder activities, both online and offline	Stakeholders from agriculture, energy, sustainability projects	Ongoing	Spain, Sweden
Use stakeholder-specific language	Translate outreach activities into local languages, adjust tone and message	Local farmers, NGOs, policymakers	Ongoing	Spain, Sweden
Incentivize stakeholders	Provide small rewards (e.g., fruit samples) to spark interest	Local farmers, experts, general public	Event-based	Spain, Sweden
Get away from stereotypes	Professional image for pilot, steer away from stereotypical associations	General public, experts, academics, influencers	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Create emotions	Use storytelling, entertainment, and emotional content for engagement	General public, NGOs, influencers, social media	Event-based	All (Spain, Germany, Sweden)
Collaborate with agricultural and energy influencers	Form strategic partnerships with farmers, cooperatives, influencers	Farmers, cooperatives, NGOs, influencers	Ongoing	Germany, Sweden
Engage policymakers	Strengthen lobbying efforts, push for budget allocations, and policy changes	Policymakers, local authorities, ministry representatives	Regular meetings	Germany, Sweden
Focus on sustainability goals	Tie project efforts to Sweden's national sustainability and climate goals	Policymakers, energy stakeholders, farmers	Ongoing	Sweden

Table 2: Summary of stakeholder engagement activities and recommendations for all three pilot regions. Based on co-creation workshops 2022 - 2024.

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